

FATIGUE SIMULATION OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES UNDER MIXED MODE CYCLIC LOADING USING A DAMAGE-MECHANICS-BASED FATIGUE ACCUMULATION MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a damage-mechanics-based fatigue model to simulate fatigue damage accumulation in composite laminates. Unlike typical Paris-law-based models, which assume pre-existing cracks and cannot predict crack initiation, the adopted model by Yashiro and Okabe employs a single constitutive equation covering the entire fatigue process—from initiation to propagation—providing a unified understanding of damage evolution. Originally developed for single-mode loading, the model is extended here to mixed-mode conditions using a new interpolation function. Mixed-mode fatigue parameters are derived from calibrated pure-mode parameters. The study involves two main stages. First, finite element calibration is performed using standard fatigue delamination onset tests, including double cantilever beam and end-notched flexure specimens. Unlike conventional approaches focused solely on propagation data, this work establishes a link between the damage-mechanics-based model and the Paris law, validating the model across both initiation and propagation phases. Simulation results align well with experimental ranges, and the model's propagation trend corresponds with the slope of the Paris law, confirming the reliability of the calibrated pure-mode parameters. In the second stage, the extended model is applied to mixed-mode fatigue using mixed-mode bending tests. Simulations are conducted to derive G-N curves across various mode mixities. The predicted fatigue behavior shows strong agreement with experimental data, with less than 6.86% deviation in the fitted G-N curve parameters. These results validate the proposed mixed-mode formulation. Overall, this study demonstrates the capability of the extended Yashiro-Okabe model to predict fatigue crack initiation and propagation under mixed-mode loading. The proposed method offers a convenient and reliable framework for simulating delamination fatigue in composite laminates across all crack growth phases.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) materials, renowned for their remarkable structural integrity and lightweight properties, have seen an increasing prevalence in aerospace applications. Despite offering superior strength compared to conventional metallic materials, the assessment of their fatigue life has become a crucial concern, given their growing usage in long-term service applications. Previous

research [1] indicates that damage patterns at stresses below the static strength significantly differ from those at static failure loads. Nevertheless, due to the intricate nature of composite materials and fatigue behaviors, characterizing fatigue evolution in CFRPs remains a relatively underdeveloped field [2, 3]. Given that no fatigue accumulation model can encompass all factors, the numerical method for assessing fatigue accumulation in composite structures remains a challenging topic. The primary aim of this paper is to introduce a numerical framework for investigating the intricate mechanisms of fatigue accumulation in CFRPs.

In order to account for the discontinuous feature of material fracture, the cohesive zone model (CZM) has emerged as a popular approach for evaluating damage in structures with plastic properties. Dugdale [4] and Barenblatt [5] laid the foundational concepts of CZM, describing the yielding behavior of stresses around the crack tip. Based on the notion of yielding stress, Hillerborg et al. [6] introduced a traction-displacement relationship for fracture energy within the cohesive zone. Numerous constitutive equations for CZM have been developed [7, 8]. In this paper, Geubelle and Taylor's model [7] is adopted as the damage model for CFRP structures, as further detailed in the subsequent section.

Concerning the prediction of fatigue damage, fatigue accumulation law combined with CZM stands as the primary tool in related research. Generally, fatigue evolution models can be categorized into two primary groups: Paris-law-based and micromechanical models. The Paris law [9], originally proposed for metallic fatigue, has proven to be suitable for predicting fatigue crack growth in FRP materials [10, 11]. Several studies [12–14] have developed modified versions of the Paris law to predict damage evolution under cyclic loading, incorporating cohesive elements. However, Paris-law-based methods cannot predict crack initiation and necessitate additional initiation criteria, as they assume the presence of cracks. Additionally, integrating the Paris law with CZM requires the use of a characteristic length [12–14] to calculate damage accumulation within the damaged area. However, both the characteristic length and mesh size can significantly influence the simulation results. Recognizing the limitations of the Paris law, damage-mechanics-based models have been developed to characterize all phases of fatigue growth. Nojavan et al. [15] introduced a microscopic model considering local states of cohesive stresses and displacement jumps of CZM. Okabe and Yashiro [16] also proposed a damage-mechanics-based fatigue law applicable to delamination and in-ply matrix cracking. An extended model based on Okabe and Yashiro's equation is integrated into the numerical framework presented in this paper.

However, the original model was developed for single-mode loading and does not account for the complexities of mixed-mode loading. In this case, sets of fatigue parameters of different modes needs to be conducted once the loading condition is changed, but implementing mixed mode loading tests is expensive and time-consuming. Considering the inconvenience, obtaining mixed mode parameters from the results of pure mode tests is an important work for establishing an easy-to-use fatigue simulation program. In this study, the fatigue parameters of extended Yashiro-Okabe model are calibrated by delamination onset data. After the FE calibrations, the fatigue propagation simulations are also performed to investigate the fracture behavior after crack initiation. The simulation data is compared to the experimental results in the phase of Paris law. Using simulation results in initiation and propagation, our extended fatigue model can be proved applicable in all phases of fatigue growth.

2 NUMERICAL METHOD

2.1 Numerical Program

The fatigue simulation program in this paper is established upon the work by Nagashima and Sawada [17], as illustrated in Fig. 1. Cohesive elements are employed to simulate delamination on the interfaces. In the quasi-3D program, FE models are established on a 2D-based mesh and subsequently extended into 3D elements along the thickness direction using level set functions. Detailed equations of the numerical framework can be found in [17-19].

2.2 Constitutive Equation of CZM

In this paper, we incorporate Geubelle and Taylor's model [7] as the constitutive equation for CZM within the numerical program. To assess damage in the cohesive zone, a damage variable D is defined

as follows:

$$D = \max \left(D_{\max}, \min \left(1, \sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta_I}{\delta_{IC}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta_{II}}{\delta_{IIC}} \right)^2} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Here, δ_I and δ_{II} represent the relative displacements in mode I and mode II, respectively, and D_{\max} signifies the maximum D stored at each integration point. The traction-separation law of CZM can be expressed as:

$$\tau_i = \frac{(1 - D) \tau_{iC}}{D} \delta_i \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), τ_{iC} and δ_{iC} represent the cohesive strengths and critical relative displacements, respectively. The use of the maximum function ensures that D mono-tonically increases and cannot decrease. Once D reaches 1, the integration point on the cohesive element fails and separates, indicating the crack growth.

2.3 Fatigue Accumulation Law

This paper introduces an extended version of the fatigue accumulation law originally proposed by Okabe and Yashiro [16]. In this fatigue model, the damage variable D is treated as a function of the number of loading cycles, N . Consequently, the fatigue accumulation law is expressed in the form of the accumulation rate, dD/dN , as follows:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = \alpha_m \frac{F^{\beta_m}}{(1 - D)^{\gamma_m}} \quad (3)$$

In this equation, α_m , β_m , and γ_m are mixed mode fatigue parameters that are determined through FE calibration using experimental data. Typically, these parameters can only be obtained from mixed mode experiments when using Okabe and Yashiro's model. However, in this study, we propose an interpolation equation for mixed mode loading based on pure mode parameters:

$$\alpha_m = \sqrt{\left(\alpha_I \frac{\delta_I}{\delta_m} \right)^2 + \left(\alpha_{II} \frac{\delta_{II}}{\delta_m} \right)^2} \quad (4)$$

Here, α_I and α_{II} represent α under pure mode I and II, respectively. Using Eq. (4), α_m can be determined using data from pure mode tests, providing a more practical approach to determine the mixed mode parameters. Similarly, β_m and γ_m are calculated in a similar manner as in Eq. (4). In Eq. (3), a dimensionless variable of stress state, F , is introduced for evaluating the states of stresses in cohesive zone:

$$F = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\tau_{I\max}}{\tau_{IC}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{II\max}}{\tau_{IIC}} \right)^2} \quad (5)$$

Here, $\tau_{I\max}$ and $\tau_{II\max}$ represent the maximum local cohesive stresses in mode I and II, respectively, and they are stored at each integration point. By storing the local stresses and displacements in data arrays, the damage rate of the cohesive zone can be calculated for each computed cycle.

2.4 Cycle jump strategy

To enhance the computational efficiency of fatigue simulations, a cycle jump strategy, adapted from [15, 19], has been incorporated into the numerical framework. The simulation starts at cycle number $N = 1$, utilizing an implicit static solver. The applied loading on the model is linearly ramped up until reaching the maximum loading. Subsequently, the increment for the next cycle, ΔN , is determined using the following equation:

$$\Delta N = \frac{\Delta D_{max}}{\left(\frac{dD_i}{dN}\right)_{max}} \quad (6)$$

Here, $\left(\frac{dD_i}{dN}\right)_{max}$ represents the maximum $\frac{dD_i}{dN}$ among all integration points in the cohesive elements and XFEM segments. Once ΔN is determined, the array of the damage variable can be updated as follows:

$$D_i = D_{i-1} + \Delta N \left(\frac{dD_i}{dN}\right)_{i-1} \quad (7)$$

As the cycle number increases ($N > 1$), the external loading applied to the simulation model remains constant, forming a load envelope for the core implicit solver of the fatigue numerical program. This updating process is repeated within the fatigue simulation loop until the maximum cycle number is reached.

Figure 1: A scheme of modelling and extrusion process for the quasi-3D FE program.

3 NUMERICAL MODELS

To demonstrate the utility of the proposed fatigue accumulation model, we have selected the double cantilever beam (DCB), end-notched flexure (ENF) and mixed mode bending (MMB) tests as the focus of this study. For comparison with simulation results, we utilize the experimental data of fatigue progression in IM7/8552 by Murri [20], O'Brien et al. [21] and Ratcliffe et al. [22]. The numerical analysis can be broken down into the following steps:

1. Calibration of α_I , β_I , and γ_I through the DCB simulation with experimental data.
2. Calibration of α_{II} , β_{II} , and γ_{II} through the ENF simulation with experimental data.
3. Fatigue propagation simulations of DCB and ENF with the calibrated parameters
4. Development of a fatigue OHT model employing the calibrated parameters.

3.1 Calibration of Mode I Fatigue Parameters

Experimental data from the technical report by Murri [20] were introduced for the calibration of mode I parameters. The fatigue double cantilever beam (DCB) test on IM7/8552 was conducted following the ASTM D6115 standard [23]. In this study, fatigue parameters were identified using the G-N curve, which de-scribes the correlation between the maximum energy release rate under fatigue loading and the onset of crack growth cycles. For the finite element (FE) model, an initial static DCB simulation was conducted to determine the maximum displacement of the static DCB test. Subsequently, displacements corresponding to various residual percentages were applied for fatigue loading. This approach enabled the determination of the comprehensive G-N curve through FE analysis, and the parameters were established by fitting the simulation data to the experimental curve via a trial-and-error procedure.

The material properties of unidirectional IM7/8552 for the simulations are listed in Table 1. The geometry and boundary conditions of the FE model are depicted in Fig. 2. The fatigue DCB test model exhibited dimensions of 178 mm in length, 25.4 mm in width, 4.5 mm in thickness, and an initial crack length of 50.8 mm. Fig. 3 displays the fatigue simulation data alongside the experimental G-N curve. The solid line represents the curve fitted to the experimental data [20], while the dots represent the simulation results, accompanied by a fitted dotted curve. Through the calibration process, the mode I

parameters were determined, resulting in $\alpha_I = 0.1689$, $\beta_I = \gamma_I = 22.495$.

3.2 Calibration of Mode II Fatigue Parameters

Experimental data from the technical report authored by O'Brien et al. [21] served as the basis for mode II calibration. The fatigue end-notched flexure (ENF) test of IM7/8552 was conducted, incorporating extension from both ASTM D7905 [24] and ASTM D6115 [23], as there is no standardized mode II fatigue test. The methodology for mode II calibration followed the same process as outlined in Section 3.1.

The geometry and boundary conditions of the finite element (FE) model are visualized in Fig. 4. Utilizing the geometric specifications provided in [21], the fatigue ENF test model had dimensions of 101.6 mm in length, 25.0 mm in width, 4.445 mm in thickness, and an initial crack length of 25.4 mm. Fig. 5 presents the fatigue simulation data alongside the experimental G-N curve. The solid line represents the curve fitted to the experimental data [21], while the dots represent the simulation results, accompanied by a fitted dotted curve. Through the calibration process, the mode II parameters were determined, resulting in $\alpha_{II} = 0.11$ and $\beta_{II} = \gamma_{II} = 12.5$.

Properties		Magnitudes
E_{11}	[GPa]	161.0
E_{22}	[GPa]	11.38
G_{12}	[GPa]	5.17
G_{23}	[GPa]	3.92
ν_{12}		0.32
ν_{23}		0.45
G_{IC}	[GPa]	0.2399
G_{IIC}	[GPa]	0.739
τ_{IC}	[GPa]	60.0
τ_{IIC}	[GPa]	90.0

Table 1: Material properties of IM7/8552.

Figure 2: FE model of fatigue DCB test.

Figure 3: G-N curve of IM7/8552 under mode I loading.

Figure 4: FE model of fatigue ENF test.

Figure 5: G-N curve of IM7/8552 under mode II loading.

3.3 Mesh sensitivity study

In Section 3.1 and 3.2, the process of calibrating mode I and II fatigue parameters are demonstrated. However, the sensitivity of mesh size to the results of FE calibration is also important. The issue of mesh convergence could result in a huge impact on the fatigue program if the simulation data is highly dependent on the element size. In Section 3.3, simulations are performed with different FE models with different element sizes. Table 2 and 3 listed the element size and number of elements for fatigue DCB and ENF simulation, respectively. In Table 2 and 3, the line with bold text is the original element size utilized in Section 3.3. The 2D views of FE models are also illustrated in Fig. 6 and 7. The G-N curves from fatigue DCB and ENF simulations across all element sizes are depicted in Fig. 8 and 9. These figures demonstrate that the delamination onset curves align with the trend of fitted experimental curves. The variations in onset cycles across different element sizes remain within a narrow range, confirming mesh convergence in the fatigue simulations using the Yashiro-Okabe model.

Element size (mm)	Number of Elements	Number of Solid Elements	Number of cohesive Elements
0.0625	257400	132000	125400
0.1	163800	84000	79800
0.125	132600	68000	64600
0.2	85800	44000	41800
0.25	70200	36000	34200

Table 2: Element size and number for fatigue DCB simulation.

Element size (mm)	Number of Elements	Number of Solid Elements	Number of cohesive Elements
0.0625	277290	142200	135090
0.1	195390	100200	95190
0.125	168090	86200	81890
0.2	115440	59200	56240
0.25	97890	50200	47690

Table 3: Element size and number for fatigue ENF simulation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: FE models for fatigue DCB with the element size of (a) 0.25 mm (b) 0.125 mm.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: FE models for fatigue ENF with the element size of (a) 0.25 mm (b) 0.125 mm.

Figure 8: G-N curves of delamination onset in fatigue DCB across different element sizes.

Figure 9: G-N curves of delamination onset in fatigue ENF across different element sizes.

4 NUMERICAL ANALYSES OF FATIGUE PROPAGATION

Using the fatigue parameters calibrated in Section 3, the simulations of fatigue propagation are performed after the fatigue onset. The curves of fatigue propagation rate relative to the input energy release rate are established. A comparative analysis of numerical results and experimental data is shown in Fig. 10, where the simulation results are represented by a blue line, experimental data by grey dots, and the fitted Paris law curve by a black line. As indicated in Fig. 10, the simulation data fits well within the range of the experimental data, and the trend of the simulation curve closely matches the slope of the fitted Paris law curve. The results depicted in Fig. 10 confirm that the pure mode fatigue parameters calibrated from the initiation tests are effectively applicable in the fatigue propagation phase.

Figure 10: Curve of fatigue propagation rate to the residual energy release rate in (a) fatigue DCB and (b) fatigue ENF test and simulation.

5 VALIDATION OF FATIGUE BEHAVIOR PREDICTION FOR MODE MIXITY

The applicability of the proposed model to crack initiation and propagation under pure modes is validated in Sections 3 and 4. For mixed-mode loading, Eq. (4) is introduced as an extension of Yashiro and Okabe's model [16], and requires validation using experimental mixed-mode data. In this subsection, a finite element model of the fatigue mixed-mode bending (MMB) test is developed to predict fatigue behavior. The numerical results are compared with experimental data reported by Ratcliffe and Johnston

[22]. Simulations are performed at various levels of G_{max} , corresponding to 50%, 40%, 35%, 30%, and 25% of the static critical energy release rate G_C , defined as the sum of G_I and G_{II} at the static critical load.

Following the workflow in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, the compliance of the MMB model is monitored during the simulation to construct the G–N curves. These curves, corresponding to different mixed-mode ratios, are obtained from numerical analysis and compared with the experimental data. The FE model geometry and boundary conditions are shown in Fig. 11. Mixed-mode parameters are calculated at each cycle using the calibrated pure-mode parameters and Eq. (4). The simulation results are presented in Fig. 12, where triangular markers denote numerical results, while circular markers and dashed lines represent experimental data from [22]. As shown, the predicted fatigue life aligns closely with the experimental curves, confirming the validity of the proposed mixed-mode extension.

Figure 11: FE model of fatigue MMB test.

Figure 12: G–N curve of IM7/8552 under mixed mode loadings (a) Mixed mode ratio of 0.8 (b) Mixed mode ratio of 0.5 (c) Mixed mode ratio of 0.2.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a numerical scheme that combines cohesive elements with a damage-mechanics-based approach to predict fatigue evolution in laminated composites. The proposed framework effectively captures both crack initiation and propagation under cyclic loading. An extended version of the fatigue accumulation law, based on the work of Yashiro and Okabe [16], is implemented within the numerical program. The calibration methodology developed in this study enables the derivation of mixed-mode fatigue parameters from pure mode tests, with a proposed interpolation equation that simplifies the process. This extension facilitates the application of the fatigue CZM to cases involving varying mode mixities.

The numerical scheme is validated against experimental results from DCB, ENF, and MMB tests, showing good agreement with the observed fatigue behavior [20-22]. In summary, this study provides a convenient and reliable approach that leverages a damage-mechanics-based model to simulate progressive fatigue damage in composite laminates.

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